

What is difference of acknowledged entities in different disciplines? —— A case study of doctoral dissertations in Chinese humanities and social sciences discipline

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Introduction

The doctoral dissertation represents a significant scientific research achievement and is a crucial requirement for earning a Ph.D. degree. The acknowledgement section of the dissertation serves as an important source of information about the guidance and support the author received during their studies.

Through the extraction of acknowledged entities from doctoral dissertations, we can gain insight into who provides support during the doctoral education process, which can be used as a reference for designing training programs and arranging academic activities across different disciplines. Scrivener (2009) manually identified 219 acknowledged entities for doctoral dissertations in history field. Smirnova & Mayr (2022) extracted acknowledged entities from the acknowledgment texts using a named entity recognition tagger and then divided them into six categories including funding agency, grant number, individuals, university, corporation, and miscellaneous. Previous research in this area has primarily relied on manual recognition methods, but there is a lack of large-scale entity extraction and detailed analysis of dissertation acknowledgements.

In this study, we aim to extract acknowledged entities from the acknowledgement texts of doctoral dissertations in the field of social sciences in China, and to develop a fine-grained classification system to reveal differences in the distribution of acknowledged entities across different disciplines.

Method

The framework of this paper is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Framework of this study

Data collection

Based on China Doctoral Dissertations Full-text Database¹, we collected 67,359 acknowledgement texts from doctoral dissertations in 21 social science disciplines spanning from 1993 to 2020. The disciplinary distribution of acknowledgement texts is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of Acknowledgment Texts

Discipline	# Texts
Philosophy	3,628
Economics	12,487
Law	4,536
Politics	3,051
Sociology	1,017
Ethnology	631
Marxist Theory	3,494
Education	3,154
Psychology	1,311
Sports	2,084
Chinese Language and Literature	7,479
Foreign Language and Literature	1,537
Journalism and Communication	613
Art	1,905
History	3,791
Military Science	504
Management Science and Engineering	9,765
Business administration	274
Agricultural and Forestry Economics Management	3,586
Public Administration	2,381
Library and information science	131
Total	67,359

Acknowledged entity extraction

We extracted acknowledged entities from the Chinese-language dissertations using a combination of word segmentation, POS tagging, and manual selection. Firstly, we used the BaiDuNLP² tool to tag the parts of speech of the acknowledgements after segmenting the words. Secondly, we selected words that were identified as "nouns", "other proper nouns", and "organization names". Finally, we manually identified acknowledged entities from the selected nouns and proper nouns, and combined them with recognized organizations to form a list of acknowledged entities.

Acknowledged entity classification

Using the classification methods proposed by Giles & Council (2004) and considering the characteristics of doctoral dissertations, we divided the acknowledged entities into two categories: acknowledged individuals and acknowledged organizations, each with 13 subcategories. The classification system is shown in Table 2.

Results

Distribution of acknowledged entity categories

We found that the proportion of acknowledged individuals was 78% and the proportion of acknowledged organizations was 22%. "Teacher" and "Family" were the highest proportion of acknowledged individuals, which highlights the importance of guidance and support from teachers in doctoral education, as well as the importance of emotional support from family members for doctoral students. "University" was the highest proportion among acknowledged organizations, which reflects the necessity of academic materials and equipment from the university for dissertation writing. The category distribution of acknowledged entities is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Acknowledged Entity Classification

Categories	Subcategories	Entities
Individuals (78%)	Teacher	267,110
	Family	234,252
	Research group	113,585
	Friend	86,043
	Classmate	82,716
	Academic colleagues	50,386
	Review experts	286
Organizations (22%)	University	162,600
	Research institutions	30,710
	Party and government organizations	21,138
	Enterprise	12,546
	Project funding fund	8,711
	Public welfare institutions	215

High-frequency acknowledged entities

The high-frequency acknowledged entities are those who had provided a significant level of support to doctoral students. The enterprises with the highest frequency of acknowledgement were the People's Education Press and the Bank of China, which were acknowledged most frequently in the disciplines of education and economics, respectively. The People's Education Press primarily provided research materials such as textbooks for education doctors, while the Bank of China mostly provided data support and work practice opportunities for economics doctors. The project funding funds with the highest frequency were the National Natural Science Foundation of China and National Social Science Fund of China. The trend in the acknowledgement frequency of these two funds over

time is shown in Figure 2, which indicated that the frequency of acknowledgement for project funding funds has been increasing in recent years.

Figure 2. Time evolution trend of the fund's acknowledgement frequency

Disciplinary differences of acknowledged entities

By analyzing the disciplinary differences of acknowledged entities, the result shows the disciplinary differences in the academic resources required by doctoral students. The acknowledgement frequency of research group for each doctoral thesis in psychology is 2.31, which is the highest on average. The library and information science usually require text data, so the frequency of public welfare institutions in library and information science is the highest, reaching 0.02.

Conclusion

Our study extracted acknowledged entities from 21 acknowledgement texts of doctoral dissertations in the field of humanities and social sciences, and constructed a fine-grained classification system for acknowledged entities, providing a database for future studies on acknowledged entities extraction and analysis using machine learning and other methods.

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¹ <https://www.nature.com/ncomms/>

² <https://www.nature.com/ncomms/>